

Using spatial data to identify food accessibility in Lusaka, Zambia

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Abstract

The spatial dimensions of food accessibility are related to the interaction between changes in individual entitlements, or the ability to acquire food, and the availability of and accessibility to different forms of food-related infrastructure. The unavailability or periodicity of food security data, and high cost of collecting on-the-ground data, further complicates our ability to measure urban food security in rapidly growing urban areas. Leveraging and integrating spatial data on food retailer distribution, public transportation and road networks, population density, and access to electricity (nighttime lights) can provide sub-residential area scale insights into urban food accessibility and food environments - the areas where individuals acquire and consume food. We integrate a food access measure with a poverty index derived from remotely sensed data to empirically demonstrate spatial food access variability across food environments in Lusaka, Zambia. This novel spatial approach identifies areas of low food access and high poverty at a sub-residential area scale, highlighting areas that are most vulnerable to food insecurity. This method can be applied to other urban contexts to improve intervention targeting by policymakers and development practitioners. We demonstrate that highlighting the role of the spatial dimensions of food accessibility emphasizes the interaction between city planning and infrastructure, which contributes to the food environment, while also providing a means of understanding the spatial and systemic conditions that contribute to or hinder urban food security.

Keywords *spatial analysis; food retailers; food access; infrastructure; remote sensing; open data*

1 Introduction

African urban populations are expected to increase from nearly 375 million people in 2015 to over 1.25 billion people by 2050 [1]. At the same time, African urban food systems are transforming through urbanization-induced changes to the local food environment [2]. Policymakers, researchers, and development practitioners lack appropriate metrics for effectively evaluating urban food security, food environments, and targeting interventions within growing urban areas. Evaluating food environments – “...*the interface where people interact with the wider food system to acquire and consume food*” [3] – is critical for improving our understanding of the interaction between urban residents and food security, particularly for those that live in underserved urban areas, where existing systemic conditions (including the types and quality of available infrastructure) can facilitate or limit food security.

As food environments transform, there is an increasing need to improve our understanding of food systems at different spatial scales to identify opportunities for and challenges to sustainable and equitable food access [4]. This short paper makes two primary contributions related to the evaluation of urban African food accessibility and food environments. First, we develop a methodology that is applicable for urban African contexts using publicly available spatial data of varying spatial resolutions to identify spatial patterns of potential access barriers. We use publicly available spatial data to provide sub-neighborhood scale insights for comparison and identification of vulnerable food environments, which can be used to improve our understanding of how urban residents interact with the spatial layout of their city at sub-city scales. Second, we identify how this output data can be used to develop a machine learning algorithm to identify spatial food accessibility across large urban African cities that are rapidly growing in terms of population and spatial extent. This work will provide nuanced insights that will aid in situating the relationship between the spatial dimensions of food security (where poverty occurs and the spatial layout of food-related infrastructure), which can help policymakers and development practitioners more effectively target aid and development initiatives.

2 The spatial dimensions of urban food security

Analysis of the spatial dimensions of food security has led to some emphasis on what are known as food deserts – “*areas of poor access to retail provision of healthy affordable food where the population is characterized by deprivation and compound social exclusion...*” [5]. Yet, the usefulness of the food desert concept has received significant criticism. For example, the food deserts approach to food access assessment overemphasizes the role of modern food retailers (e.g., larger grocery stores or supermarkets) in food environments [6], it does not consider the complex challenges that individuals contend with in accessing food [7,8]. In the African context, the presence, number, and distribution of so many different types of food providers limit the applicability of the food deserts concept in urban African contexts [9]. Yet, the broader point of food desert analyses, that variability in the local food environment can impact household food security remains valid [10], because the spatial layout of the food environment shapes food security in variable ways.

Most food security measurement in Africa occurs at the individual-, household-, or national-level [11], but the community-level factors that make up food environments also meaningfully contribute to food security [2]. The latter finding is related to the fact that African urban food environments are made up of an array of retailers that operate at different scales, offer different foods and at different prices, and meet the variable food needs of urban residents across space [12]. Other forms of food-related infrastructure (e.g., water, energy, and transportation) are

also not uniformly distributed across or within urban landscapes [13]. Uneven patterns of development arise with some areas featuring greater levels of infrastructure development than others. This form of development can exacerbate existing urban inequities by creating areas of socio-economic segregation [14]. By neglecting the spatial layout of food-related infrastructure in urban food security assessments, we overlook crucial insights into how the local food environment shapes household food purchasing behavior and, ultimately, food security.

3 Developing a spatial food access index

In this section we describe three remotely sensed spatial data types and products that can be used to characterize urban food accessibility: socio-economic data, mobility data, and food retailer locations [6]. We focus on publicly available remotely sensed products because they can provide lower cost proxy data for decision makers and reduce data access issues.

3.1 Poverty index (socio-economic data)

Socio-economic data is necessary to identify where potentially vulnerable populations reside. The USDA's Food Access Research Atlas (FARA) partially evaluates food access based on income characteristics developed by the US Census Bureau [6]. This form of data is either non-existent, difficult to access, or expensive to collect in urban Africa [15]. We scale down two publicly available data sets to a resolution suitable for creating a sub-city scale poverty proxy. We use the publicly available WorldPop Constrained individual countries 2020 UN adjusted (100m resolution) data set for Lusaka, Zambia (Figure 1A) [16] and the *Visible and Infrared Imaging Suite Nighttime Lights (VNL)* values (Figure 1B) [17] to create a proxy socio-economic measure.

In panel C, we combine these two data sets to create a poverty index using an approach suggested by Elvidge et al. [18]. We aggregated the WorldPop values to the same resolution of the VNL data (500m), then divided the WorldPop provided population estimates by the VNL values for each pixel. We map the individual pixel values rather than aggregating the values to an administrative level, because the smallest level relevant for policy in Lusaka is the constituency level, which would eliminate the spatial variation that we aim to uncover.

By combining the high-resolution population estimates with the VNL values at a fine-scale we can develop variable sub-residential area poverty estimates for the entire city. Area A in Figure 1C represents lower to mid-range poverty values. The lowest poverty index values are in the eastern extent of the city (Area B). These are areas with low population estimates and relatively low VNL values. In areas like this we would expect to find fewer issues related to food accessibility, and overall higher household food security. The high poverty rates in Area C are identified by the interaction between high population and low VNL values (electricity use). Areas like this would likely feature poor food accessibility and low household-level food security. By combining VNL data with population estimates we mitigate some of the challenges of using VNL data to assess socio-economic and demographic conditions in urban settings that other researchers have identified, like low lighting does not always accurately represent the number of people in a place and uneven living conditions (e.g., frequent power outages), which can obscure our understanding of the urban structure of an area [19,20]. Importantly, our poverty index values are consistent with other studies from Lusaka that identified similar areas of higher urban poverty levels and food insecurity rates [21,22].

Figure 1 *A* Constrained individual countries 2020 UN adjusted WorldPop (100 m) data population estimates for Lusaka in 2020. *B* Visible and Infrared Imaging Suite Nighttime Lights (VNL) October 2020 composite data coverage (500 m) for Lusaka. *C* A poverty index created by dividing aggregated WorldPop estimates by VNL data. Darker areas indicate higher poverty. Missing data areas are government held parcels (e.g., military bases).

3.2 Mobility data

Second, mobility data is necessary for identifying how people move across the spatial layout of their local food environment. One approach is to use public transportation or road network data to create route networks for use in econometric and spatial analyses. In general, automobile ownership is relatively low overall in urban Africa, particularly so for poor households [14]. Meaning public transportation routes and road networks are necessary to include. This data can be collected using OpenStreetMap, web scraping, or collaborating with local governments. These data sets can be merged and used to create origin-destination matrices or conduct service area analyses, among other operations. Compared to Euclidean distance measurements, transportation and road network data sets are more representative of the lived experience of urban residents who must navigate around structures and natural topography.

3.3 Food retailer data

Most urban African households purchase their food from a range of retailers [12,23], but the food retail environment is rapidly changing across urban African cities [24]. Understanding this change requires identifying how spatial and temporal changes in retailer types connect with the availability and accessibility of food in a food environment. The USDA's FARA uses distance to large retailers like supercenters, supermarkets, and grocery stores as a proxy for food access, but a more appropriate African approach requires integrating the locations of formal *and* informal, large *and* smaller food retailers (e.g., public markets, small shops, and street vendors). Supermarket and public market locations can be collected using OpenStreetMap or Google Earth [25]. Collecting the locations of smaller retailers is a challenge because not all food retailers are detectable using remote sensing, like Sentinel-2. For example, household-operated shops are often indistinguishable from residential homes because of the building materials that are commonly used in African cities [26]. Collecting smaller retailer locations and data may require a geolocated retailer census, as other studies have done [2,27]. Combining this micro-survey / census data with spatial data could provide a more complete view of the local food retailer environment.

The food retailer location database used in this manuscript was developed by the first author. The supermarket, public market, and street vendor locations were originally collected in February 2020. For more information on how the supermarket and public market locations were collected, please see Blekking et al. (2023). Street vendor locations were collected during a residential area level census in six Lusaka residential areas. Inset 2 of Figure 2 shows the street vendor locations from the Kalingalinga and Helen Kaunda areas of Lusaka.

3.4 Integrating urban food accessibility data

The mobility data and retailer location data layers can be modeled together to generate a spatial food access index - a spatially explicit estimate of the interaction between households and their local food environment. Figure 2 provides an example of a spatial food access index (SFAI) for Lusaka, Zambia. This index was informed by the formal food system potential (FFSP) measure, a form of gravity model, used by Hemerijckx et al. (2022) in Kampala, Uganda. We adopt weights from the FFSP to calculate the values of food-related infrastructure. The food-related infrastructure value of a target cell is determined based on the total value of all weights from the 20 nearest cells, similar to the approach used by Hemerijckx et al (2022). Cells that contain the centroid of a public market or supermarket receive a weight of 1, while cells that intersect with a public transportation route receive a weight of 0.5. Cells that intersect with any form of road receive a 0.25. For example, a cell that contains a supermarket, intersects with a public transportation route, and has a secondary road pass through it would receive an SFAI value of 1.75. In Inset 2 (Figure 5), we give cells that contain street vendors a weight of 0.25. We then use these weights to calculate the SFAI of a target cell. The SFAI value of a target cell is calculated by summing the food infrastructure values of nearby source cells, each divided by their Euclidean distance to the target cell – the cell for which we are calculating a SFAI value. We then sum (i.e., aggregate) the food-related infrastructure values of the twenty nearest cells. This final summation provides the SFAI value for the target cell. We use a 250 m resolution to limit computational time constraints, but the index can be developed for a finer scale. Importantly, the modeled SFAI provides a base data set that can be added to as data sets become available. For instance, water or electrical utility coverage extents, food cost information, or additional retailers can be added to the modeled index as data becomes available.

Figure 2 The spatial food accessibility index (SFAI) for Lusaka, Zambia (250 m resolution). **A** A higher resolution image of the inset area from the main figure. **B** The SFAI recalculated using street vendor locations for the Kalingalinga and Helen Kaunda areas of Lusaka. Street vendor locations were collected during a residential area level census.

The SFAI identifies areas of variable food-related infrastructure accessibility within Lusaka (Figure 2). The center of Lusaka (Area A) has relatively high levels of access, while areas of lower access occur predominantly along the city’s administrative boundary. Importantly, lower accessibility areas exist between areas of high SFAI values (Area B), thus the SFAI indicates uneven access to food-related infrastructure at a fine-scale. The highest areas of access (darker colors) indicate areas where public markets, supermarkets, and public transportation routes exist within the same local area. Panel A illustrates how within an individual residential area there is food access variability, indicating the suitability of the SFAI for sub-residential area, high resolution evaluation of the food environment. Our findings also suggest that street vendors or other smaller retailers enhance areas with already high food access, rather than fill in spatial gaps. In panel B, including street vendors in the SFAI calculation increases the SFAI values in the immediate area, but their concentrated presence does little to increase accessibility in the residential areas to the north and northeast. In this context, the availability of street vendors enhances accessibility, but the extent to which they contribute to spatial access in areas where there are no public markets, supermarkets, or intersections where public transportation is unclear.

3.5 Integrating spatial food environments with poverty

Using a geographically-weighted Pearson correlation (GWC), we examine the SFAI and poverty index across space in Lusaka to understand the relationship between socio-economic standing and food accessibility (Figure 3). First, we aggregated the 250m SFAI values to 500m (the poverty index resolution) to reduce computational constraints, but we could have calculated a finer resolution. We then created groups of SFAI and poverty index values by categorizing cells based on the upper half and lower half of their respective ranges (panel A). For instance, the low access and high poverty categorization contains the lower half of the SFAI values and the higher half of the poverty index values. Panel B represents the GWCs. The GWC is a form of moving window analysis, where a matrix of correlations is calculated on a subset of the data based on geographic proximity [28]. The data is subset based on a geographic distance threshold for a target cell. We use a bandwidth of 3km – approximately one-third of the distance across Lusaka. This

means the GWC for a specific target cell will include all the poverty index and SFAI values of the neighboring cells within 3km. For all the cells within that threshold, we calculated distances from the target cells to each neighboring cell. These distances act as spatial weights, which define how much influence one location has on another in the correlation calculation. The calculated GWCs represent the relationship between poverty and food access. We then combine the high access, high poverty and low access, high poverty categorizations and the GWC coefficients together (panel C of Figure 3).

Figure 3 A The SFAI (access) and PI (poverty) categorizations. B The geographically weighted Pearson correlation coefficients between the SFAI and PI values. C The high access, high poverty and low access, high poverty categorizations overlaid on the GWC value. Areas where a low access, high poverty category overlap negative GWC values are most vulnerable to food insecurity.

4 Results and discussion

Our results suggest that areas with high access and high poverty are often located nearer to the city center (Area A in Figure 3), while areas with low access and high poverty tend to exist on

the periphery of Lusaka's boundary (Area B). Area A, in northwest Lusaka is classified as high access, high poverty but the relationship between SFAI and poverty index varies from slightly negative to moderately positive. The varied, but generally positive, GWC between SFAI and poverty index in Area A is due to the proximity of several public transportation routes, public markets, and supermarkets interacting with moderate levels of poverty. In areas like this, household food accessibility is likely inhibited due to economic barriers, rather than the physical unavailability of food-related infrastructure.

Area B, near the western edge of the city, is classified as low access, high poverty with moderately negative underlying correlations. This is important for two reasons. First, in this area, the availability of food-related infrastructure is a limiting factor. To assuage food accessibility challenges here, food-related infrastructure investment is required. This requires a holistic approach involving retailers, water, energy, and other infrastructure. Second, this suggests that using spatial data for sub-city scale food environment measurement works particularly well in low access, high poverty areas. However, solely using the GWC approach may not work well in areas of high access and low poverty (Area C), because these areas also represent an inverse relationship, albeit with high access and low poverty. To limit this challenge, it is preferable to use the SFAI and PI categorizations (panel A) to target initial areas where the GWC will be used, thus enabling broad classification *and* fine-scale assessment of access and poverty. Our spatially-explicit approach to measuring urban food environments can improve targeting by differentiating between the need for interventions aimed at improving availability or accessibility.

5 Conclusion and next steps

When combined in spatially explicit analyses, population, transportation, and food retailer data can provide city-wide and neighborhood-level measurement of urban food accessibility. Our findings show that food access barriers arise from both economic constraints *and* limited food infrastructure, suggesting that high-resolution spatial analysis can be used as a screening tool to target on-the-ground surveys or interventions specifically focused on food security. This method is adaptable to other similarly-sized cities throughout Africa. Importantly, this method provides increasingly important data to support sustainable, equitable urban planning and policy development, like how FARA is used in the United States. However, our approach does not identify how the household characteristics impact the relationship between household food access and community-level infrastructure across space.

We plan to use these Lusaka data sets and develop others for the region to target household surveys in areas of high poverty and (low) high infrastructure in the coming year. This effort will improve our understanding of how socio-economic conditions and local infrastructure interact across space and contribute to food access at variable scales. We will use this data to train a geospatial AI model that can be used to estimate food accessibility in similarly-sized African cities and track food access and food-related infrastructure changes longitudinally.

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